

FORMATION STAGES OF THE HISTORY OF THE ART OF CONDUCTING

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Annotation: This article shows that the conducting activity is a historical process of formation, that conducting is considered to be the most difficult musical specialty, that it requires a whole set of knowledge, abilities, personal qualities and a wide range of management in the structure of professional activity, that conductors need tempo, it is suggested that it can show dynamic indicators, melodic contours.

Key words: conducting, musical sounds, conducting art, tempo, rhythmic lines, dynamic indicators, choirmaster, tact.

Conducting, which takes on such tasks as unifying a musical team and providing a creative ensemble, is considered to be the most difficult musical specialty. Because conducting requires a whole range of knowledge, abilities, personal qualities, and a wide range of management types in the structure of professional activity.

Conducting-creative activity has been formed in the process of long historical evolution. Despite the fact that conducting was formed as an independent form of musical creativity only in the second half of the 19th century, its history goes back a long time. The essence of conducting - to express music with a movement - is based on the psychophysiological characteristics of human nature. Musical sounds cause involuntary movement of human muscles (facial expressions, movements, leg movements, body movements). Ancient musical culture was based on such things.

In the pre-civilization period, the genre foundations of music can be seen mainly in dances. During the dance, the ancient man's body movements and expression of the rhythm through the means at hand (wood, stone, shells) serve as the main basis of the art of conducting. The demand for aesthetic experiences characteristic of humanity has led to the formation of a community similar to an ensemble, and this, in turn, has created the need for a leader who manages this community. Management of such a creative team was carried out using the percussion-noise acoustic method, that is, by beating the rhythm with hands, feet, sticks and showing the count. The control of the collective performance is harmonized by giving a similar tempo. This category, the man who led those creative ensembles, was a symbol of the conductor's profession, and his actions

served as the manager's main management method, in addition to percussion instruments.

The next stage of the development of conducting corresponds to the period of the most ancient civilizations (Egypt, India, the Greek state, Rome), and the ancient Greek theater serves as its main stage. In these theaters, the choir was the main component, and the leader of the choir (the luminary) stood on the podium and played the role of a conductor, showing metrical accents and hitting the coturn. During these periods, more vocal than dancing takes the main place in music, and new conducting behaviors develop to show the tone and intensity of music. Such a system of methods for managing the performance of musical groups was called "chieronomy" or "chironomy" (Greek cheir - hand).

A conductor using hieronomy could show the performers tempo, rhythmic lines, dynamic indicators, and melodic contours (up and down directions of the melody). The use of this chironomy replaced the percussion-noise instruments that the conductor needed, and the conductor moved to hand movements.

In the Middle Ages, the art of conducting, like other areas of professional creative culture, developed under the patronage of the church. Music has always been an important and integral part of worship. The hierarchical system of the medieval priesthood created a similarly defined system of positions in the field of conducting. For example, a highly respected chief conductor (primitserius) was presented with a weighty cane indicating his rank. This cane will later become a conductor's baton.

The next period of development of conducting will be very difficult. There were a lot of people against him, because the "noise" caused by hitting the remote control with a cane during conducting would destroy the music. In the process of solving the problem, musicians try many "quieter" things that can be used in place of the cane. One such solution was called a "card" and was a form of wrapping several notes.

During the Middle Ages, hieronomy had a new period of development. The reason is that the free-flowing metric of the Gregorian choir, formed by this time, was very suitable for the music, which was completely subordinated to the word. transition from noisy control to noiseless control was a very important stage in the development of conducting art. In the 17th century in Italy, the basic theories of conducting, most importantly the scheme of timing, begin to emerge. The development of the notation system has a great influence on their occurrence. The most important discovery in the concept of time in music - tact was created. The structure of the tact has strengthened the conductors' desire to

present all the contributions within it with sufficient clarity and at the same time to make them a whole. The advent of metered notation increased the demand for a more precise representation of the contributions in a measure, to achieve precision by seeing their metrical structure. The creation of a clocking scheme is related to heiromania. Precisely in keiromania, it was introduced to indicate the meter without noise, with hand movements up, down, right, left.

A new era in the art of conducting is associated with the term basic bass. This fundamentally changed the practice of conducting. This means that the management of the ensemble is now carried out under the leadership of the harpsichordist, by playing the main bass. It became the task of the harpsichordist to provide the tempo with the change of harmonic sounds through the dynamic separation of metrical accents. Many conductors, including the great Johann Sebastian Bach, directed the ensemble with glances, head movements, and occasional hand movements while playing the harpsichord. Here is a description of such conducting by an unknown contemporary of Johann Sebastian Bach: "How Bach conducted thirty or even forty performers at the same time, indicating the time by nodding to one side, it is difficult to imagine another side being pointed by a kick and a third side being controlled by the index finger. He was sitting in the very center of the music sounds, when something went wrong, he would stop them, correct the flaws and continue."

But this kind of conducting had its flaws. Due to the fact that the conductor was playing the harpsichord at the same time, his influence on the team was limited enough. Due to this, in the first quarter of the 18th century, dual conducting began to take shape. In this case, the violinist-concertmaster or choirmaster acted as the second conductor while leading the ensemble along with the main conductor-harpsichordist. It is worth noting that this type of management of collective performance is still preserved as one of the types of rehearsal. Currently, double conducting is found in musical-dramatic genres such as a choir behind the scenes or an orchestra on stage, as well as in cases where the composition of performers is so large that it is difficult to cover with one conductor.

Since the second half of the 18th century, the violinist-concertmaster has been the leader of the instrumental group. He played his instrument and performed the duties of a conductor with his bow. Leading the ensemble by playing the violin enriched the conducting technique and had a significant impact. The violinist-concertmaster, while showing the expressive parts of the music, used the methods that were convenient for him, that were convenient for the bow

technique of the violinist. Thus, a system of conditional actions is created that is understandable to all representatives of the musical team.

The further complexity of the musical language, the widespread use of musical-expressive symbols by composers forced the conductor to free himself from the simultaneous performance of musical instruments in order to deal with his main task, which is to fully reveal the creative essence of a musical work. . In the implementation of the new direction of conducting, it is important to distinguish it as a separate musical specialty. From the first half of the 19th century, the conductor's baton began to be widely used. The demand for a more precise representation of the metrical contributions of the takt grew stronger. The art of conducting was enriched with unique musical-creative techniques that express conditional actions. Progressive was a unique new rhythmic way of conducting an orchestra based on tact, which replaced the noisy method of conducting. The space and time form of the beat allowed to show various interrelationships of strong and weak contributions in the beat, thereby helping to create musical sentences. Tapping is gradually enriched with the help of expressive movements with emotional and meaningful fillings formed during the interaction of the performers. The development of musical creativity, especially the development of orchestral music founded by great composers such as Ludwig van Beethoven, Berlioz, Felix Mendelssohn, Richard Wagner, certainly increased the demand for the development of conducting techniques.

References:

1. Akbarov I.A "Music dictionary". Literary and art publishing house named after G. Ghulam. 1987.
2. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.

